

Towards Fully Roll-to-roll Printable Organic Solar Cells: Optimization of Gravure Printed Electron Transport Layer

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ABSTRACT

For fully roll-to-roll (R2R) printed flexible organic solar cells, mechanical robustness and solvent compatibility of the interfacial layers with the active layer and top electrodes remain major challenges. In this work, we present an electron transport layer (ETL) material based on zinc-ion-chelated polyethyleneimine (PEI-Zn) that combines mechanical robustness, performance and compatibility with roll-to-roll printing. The PEI-Zn formulation is tailored to an industrial-scale gravure printing process by employing ethanol as processing solvent and refining the printing process parameters and ink formulation. The scalability of the PEI-Zn ETL material and the gravure printing process is demonstrated by R2R printing of PEI-Zn ETLs over hundreds of meters on flexible substrate. Fully printable non-fullerene organic solar cells with R2R gravure printed PEI-Zn ETL and PM6:Y12 active layer are fabricated entirely in ambient conditions, retaining a high fill factor of 65%.

1 | Introduction

Organic photovoltaics (OPV) has emerged as an exciting complementary technology to conventional silicon-based photovoltaics. Their unique features such as flexibility, semitransparency, lightweight and solution processability open pathways for a variety of complementary applications to conventional solar cells. Over the past decade, intensive research effort has been put into further enhancing OPV performance, recently exceeding 20% power conversion efficiency (PCE) on a laboratory scale [1-4]. This is a remarkable success, bridging the gap to conventional technologies [5], but most of these record efficiency devices are fabricated in lab-scale, using glass substrates with spin-coating in glovebox environment and relying on vacuum technology for electrode deposition, while devices using scalable production technologies are still lagging behind [6-8]. Thus, one of the key benefits of OPV materials – the ability to process from solution, allowing high throughput processes in ambient conditions – is neglected.

Besides efficiency and long-term stability, the main focus of lab-scale organic solar cells, cost efficiency and production scalability are key requirements for successfully integrating OPVs into everyday life applications.

Conventional printing methods, such as gravure printing, flexo- and screen-printing offer means of high throughput, large-area mass production, especially when the substrate is employed as a web, better known as roll-to-roll (R2R)

printing. However, slot-die coating and blade coating are the predominant methods used to produce large-area organic solar cells (OSCs), due to their straightforward, simple processing and wide range of compatible ink formulations [8-13]. These coating technologies need additional processing steps to create 2D patterned layers, such as laser ablation and typical processing speeds are orders of magnitude lower compared to conventional R2R printing [14,15].

Gravure printing offers a viable and scalable processing alternative to these coating technologies for the deposition of functional layers for organic solar cells and modules. It enables high-speed, high-resolution roll-to-roll processing, but also comes with a series of processing constraints and challenges when it comes to ultrathin functional layers on flexible substrates [14,16-18]. Compared to non-impact coating technologies, such as slot-die coating and blade coating, R2R gravure printing subjects underlying layers to mechanical stress, thereby requiring enhanced mechanical integrity and interfacial adhesion of the selected functional layers. Furthermore, R2R printing processes require flexible substrates, which restricts the maximum annealing temperatures, consequently narrowing the range of compatible functional materials. In addition, the functional materials have to be formulated as inks specifically tailored to the requirements of the respective printing process [14]. Gravure printing requires low and well-controlled viscosity, shear behavior, a compatible solvent system with appropriate evaporation rate and wetting behavior.

Besides the active layer, transport layers are crucial for performance, efficiency and stability of OSCs [19-21]. Especially a defect-free, homogeneous and smooth electron transport layer (ETL) is of great importance in the inverted structure, since its layer quality directly influences the quality of the subsequently printed active layer. Most commercially available ETL materials are optimized for spin coating applications and cannot directly be transferred to printing methods.

Metal oxide nanoparticles or sol-gel zinc oxide (ZnO) are widely used electron-transport layer materials for OSC production [22]. Due to the processing constraints, specifically the required annealing temperatures up to 200° C, these materials are not well compatible with R2R gravure printing on flexible substrates, which is restricted to ~150° C for PET-based substrates.

In this work, we present a gravure printable formulation of PEI-Zn as ETL material alternative to ZnO nanoparticles. Furthermore, we demonstrate fully printed OSCs in inverted layer structure on flexible PET-foil substrates.

2 | Results and Discussion

2.1 | Materials and Printing Process

For the realization of fully printed flexible OSCs, the inverted device structure is preferred [23]. While conventional OSCs reached record efficiencies, OSCs in inverted structure are considered favorable in context of industrially scalable processes on flexible substrates and show better long-term stability [24-26].

Therefore, in this work, the focus is on the inverted device structure with a layer-stack tailored to printing processes (Figure 1a). An image of the printed OSC is shown in Figure 1b and the printing and post-treatment steps are depicted in Figure 1c for fully printed flexible OSCs fabricated in this work. As flexible substrate a poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) foil of 125 μm thickness, coated with an indium tin oxide (ITO) / metal / indium tin oxide (IMI) layer as transparent electrode material is selected. The ETL materials, a commercially available ZnO nanoparticle solution and an ethanol-based Zinc ion (Zn²⁺)-chelated polyethyleneimine (PEI) solution are deposited on the IMI-substrate via R2R gravure printing. The active layer (AL) material of choice in this work, the donor:acceptor (D:A) blend PM6:Y12, is subsequently gravure printed on top of the ETL. PM6:Y12 is chosen due to its solubility in non-chlorinated solvents such as o-xylene [27], its stability in ambient-air processing conditions (Figure S1) and its superior photodegradation stability [28], which is of great interest for upscaling production conditions. Halogenated solvents, such as chloroform (CF), chlorobenzene and dichlorobenzene are widely used in lab-scale environment for OSC fabrication. However, in industrial-scale processes, the use of chlorinated solvents poses a series of problems, such as health and safety risks in open or semi-open environments, complex waste management and extensive investments for ventilation, solvent recovery and environmental compliance. We produced devices with gravure printed PM6:Y12 ALs processed from chloroform and o-xylene with comparable performance in this work.

After gravure printing the AL, the printed substrate web is cut to smaller sheets. For the hole transport layer (HTL) a

FIGURE 1 | (a) Layer-by-layer device structure. (b) Photograph of fully printed solar cell. (c) Schematic diagram of printing and post-treatment processes

bilayer approach is chosen, consisting of a thin layer of BM-HTL-1 deposited by slot-die coating and a thicker layer of screen printed poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) polystyrene sulfonate (PEDOT:PSS). While the thin layer of BM-HTL-1 enables good wetting on the AL material, the thick PEDOT:PSS layer serves as protective layer, thus enabling subsequent screen printing of the silver top electrode (TE). In contrast, a single layer HTL of printed PEDOT:PSS on top of the AL results in a significant open-circuit voltage (V_{OC}) drop, due to an energy mismatch between the highest occupied molecular orbital level of the AL and the printed PEDOT:PSS HTL [29,30]. In addition, printable PEDOT:PSS formulations are usually water-based, thus leading to wetting and film formation issues on the hydrophobic active-layer material.

For the deposition of ETL, AL and BM-HTL-1, a curtain of pressurized nitrogen is applied to the substrate via an air knife, directly before ink deposition. This serves the purpose of an additional cleaning from dust particles, as well as counteracting the influence of high humidity conditions in ambient environment. After the deposition of the BM-HTL-1 interlayer with a layer thickness of ~50 nm, a thick layer of PEDOT:PSS (~600 nm) is screen printed on top. Finally, silver top electrodes with a thickness of 3 μm are applied via screen printing.

2.2 | Optimization of Gravure-printable ETL

The choice of suitable functional materials for scalable printing processes for OSCs is determined by various restrictions. First, post-treatment temperatures are limited. PET-based substrates, the standard material for cost-

efficient R2R OSC production, are restricted to a maximum processing temperature of ~150°C [31]. Secondly, the printed films must be mechanically robust and exhibit strong interlayer adhesion. Since conventional R2R printing methods are used to create a multilayer stack of tens or few hundreds of nanometer thin layers, the functional layers must be robust enough to withstand mechanical stress when being printed on or transferred over transport rollers. Thirdly, the materials have to be formulated as inks matching the requirements of the respective printing method, such as suitable volatilization rate of the solvent, surface tension and viscosity.

For the realization of fully printed flexible OSCs, different ETL material ink formulations are investigated. The compatibility of these ink formulations with the gravure printing process is evaluated in this section with a gravure proof-printing setup. ZnO nanoparticle (NP) suspension in alcohol is the most commonly used ETL material for R2R processing on flexible substrates [22]. A commercially available ZnO NP suspension is modified to meet the gravure printing process requirements and compared to a promising metal-ion-chelated polymer ETL material [32]. The ethanol-based ZnO nanoparticle solution as purchased works well for processing via spin-coating but does not meet the rheological requirements of the gravure printing process. Therefore, 1-butanol is added to the formulation to adjust the volatilization rate and 1 wt% high molecular weight (1300k) poly(vinylpyrrolidone) (PVP) is added to increase the NP ink's viscosity according to the previous work on gravure printed ZnO nanoparticle solution by Wang et al. [33]. The modified ZnO formulations is gravure printed on IMI-PET substrate using a 14 ml/m² gravure

FIGURE 2 | (a) Impressions of gravure printing form cell walls in ZnO:PVP Layer. (b) Impressions of gravure printing form cell walls in PEI-Zn Layer. (c) Adhesion of ZnO:PVP to the substrate. (d) Adhesion of PEI-Zn to the substrate.

form at 0.2 m/s web speed to create a smooth layer of ZnO with 30 nm thickness. However, the printed ZnO ETL does not adhere well to the substrate and can be easily wiped off after thermal treatment at 140 °C (Figure 2c). The layer adhesion was tested by wiping with a Q-tip (red markings in Figure 2c, d).

The processing temperature of PET-based substrates is limited. The maximum processing temperatures for thermally stabilized PET substrates is given in literature with 150 °C [31], but ultimately depends on more factors, such as web tension and time of heat exposure. To test the processing limits of the IMI-PET substrate, it was run through the R2R machine with a web-speed of 0.2 m/s at different web tension settings (30/60/100 N/m) and increasing drying unit temperatures from 120 °C to 175 °C. The temperature was measured directly on the substrate via infrared sensor. Afterwards, sheet resistance of the IMI-substrate is taken and compared against its original value (~10 Ω/sq). As shown in Figure 3, the maximum processing temperature is strongly dependent on web tension. As the substrate temperature increases, the substrate elongates and finally damages the IMI layer, drastically reducing its conductivity. Highest substrate temperature at 160°C without destroying the IMI layer is achieved at low web tension of 30 N/m.

Consequently, the thermal processing window for ZnO layers on flexible PET substrates is significantly constrained, precluding the use of conventional annealing temperatures of 200 °C commonly employed in laboratory-scale device fabrication. This is a critical limitation, since insufficient thermal annealing of gravure printed ZnO layers leads to mechanical damage induced during the subsequent gravure printing of the AL. Figure 2(a) shows strong impressions of the gravure printing form cell walls in the ZnO:PVP layer after AL layer deposition.

FIGURE 3 | Web-tension dependent thermal stability of IMI-PET substrate at a web speed of 0.2 m/s.

Ultraviolet-ozone (UVO) post-treatment was employed as an additional strategy to improve the adhesion of ZnO to the substrate. UVO exposure of ZnO films is commonly used to remove residual organic stabilizers and capping agents [34], decomposition of organic ligands, densifying particles [35], and promote desorption of oxygen and water

[36]. For gravure-printed ZnO layers, it improves adhesion to the substrate to some extent (Figure S2(d–f)). The impact of UVO exposure on device performance is shown in Figure 4. Moderate exposure largely preserves the photovoltaic parameters but does not sufficiently enhance the mechanical stability of the ZnO films. In contrast, stronger exposure leads to a clear deterioration of device performance. Excessive UVO is known to generate additional oxygen-related defects at the ZnO surface [34], promoting non-radiative voltage losses and hindering charge extraction. Accordingly, devices subjected to strong UVO exposure show a pronounced reduction in V_{OC} and fill factor (FF), together with an increase in transport resistance [37].

FIGURE 4 | Influence of UVO post-treatment of ZnO:PVP layers on OSC performance. Devices were fabricated using spin-coating with a layer structure of glass/ITO/ZnO:PVP/PM6:Y12/BM-HTL-1/Ag.

Due to insufficient adhesion and mechanical integrity, gravure-printed ZnO:PVP layers are not well compatible with the requirements of roll-to-roll print processing. We therefore focus on an alternative PEI-Zn based ETL material.

In 2020 Qin et al. presented a robust metal-ion-chelated polymer ETL material [32]. Their material formulation is composed of the amine-containing polymer polyethyleneimine (PEI) and zinc acetate dihydrate dissolved in 2-methoxyethanol and a small amount of water (10 µl per ml) to increase the solubility of zinc acetate. Zn^{2+} chelates with nitrogen atoms of PEI, reducing the chemical reactivity of PEI towards different active layer materials. The formulation is denoted as PEI-Zn. This material is a promising alternative to ZnO nanoparticle solutions for fully printed OSCs due to its robustness. However, the formulation in 2-methoxyethanol is not suitable for gravure printing, due to its high boiling point (125 °C), resulting in inhomogeneous layers and poor edge quality (Figure S3(a)). In addition, 2-methoxyethanol is highly toxic and thus not suitable for industrially scalable processes in ambient conditions.

We developed a gravure printable formulation of PEI-Zn, by using ethanol as a non-toxic solvent base. The ethanol-

FIGURE 5 | J-V-characteristics of printed devices using ZnO:PVP and PEI-Zn ETLs. Printed devices were fabricated with proof-printing equipment according to the description in section 2.1. Active layer material PM6:Y12 was dissolved in chloroform.

based PEI-Zn iteration is compatible with gravure printing and results in more homogeneous layers with better edge quality due to its lower boiling point and increased volatilization rate (Figure S3(b)). To compare the adhesion and mechanical integrity of the ethanol-based PEI-Zn formulation to printed ZnO layers, the formulations are gravure printed on IMI-PET substrate. While ZnO:PVP layers can be easily wiped off and completely removed using a Q-tip (Figure 2(c)), the PEI-Zn layer adheres well to the substrate (Figure 2(d)). To further test the mechanical robustness of the printed PEI-Zn layers and its compatibility to the subsequent gravure printing process of the active layer material, *o*-xylene and chloroform solvents are gravure printed on top of the PEI-Zn layers to simulate the gravure printing process of the AL. While the gravure printing process of the AL leaves strong impressions in the ZnO layer and partially destroys it, the impressions are hardly noticeable in the PEI-Zn layers (Figure 2(a) and (b)).

Figure 5 shows the comparison of printed devices fabricated from ZnO-based and PEI-Zn based ETL material. This shows that PEI-Zn can be used as ETL material alternative to ZnO, yielding similar performance, but offering superior mechanical stability for R2R gravure printing processes.

2.3 | Transition from Proof-printing to R2R Gravure Printed ETL

Transferring laboratory-scale ink formulations processed with spin-coating to R2R gravure printing requires careful control over both chemical composition and solvent system, as these parameters directly influence solubility, film formation, and ultimately device performance. In particular, PEI-Zn systems are highly sensitive to the Zn-to-N ratio and solvent environment. In this section, the transfer of PEI-Zn formulations from spin-coating to proof-printing and finally to industrial-scale R2R gravure printing is discussed.

Qin et al. investigated the influence of the Zn-to-N ratio in PEI-Zn formulations and found that ratios below 4:1 lead to pronounced s-shaped JV curves, while ratios above 15:1 cause the solution to turn cloudy due to oversaturation, where the $\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ cannot be fully chelated by PEI and remains partially undissolved. However, their formulation was based on 2-methoxyethanol as solvent. Although zinc acetate is reported to be reasonably soluble in ethanol^[38], its solubility is significantly lower than in 2-methoxyethanol. To improve solubility in the ethanol-based formulation used here, the water fraction was increased, and the solution was stirred at 50 °C for 2 h and ultrasonicated. Consequently, the optimal Zn-to-N ratio reported by Qin et al. does not necessarily apply to ethanol-based formulations and must be reassessed.

To investigate the effect of Zn concentration in the ethanol-based PEI-Zn formulation on crystallization and performance, we prepared four formulations with different Zn-to-N molar ratios (8:1/10:1/12:1/15:1). Spin-coated

FIGURE 6 | J-V-characteristics of devices with PEI-Zn ETL containing different Zn-to-N mole ratios. (a) Spin-coated reference cells. (b) Gravure printed flexible devices.

FIGURE 7 | R2R printing PEI-Zn. (a) Precipitation of $Zn(OH)_2$ on non-heated gravure printing form. (b) defective layer of R2R printed PEI-Zn in 15:1 Zn-to-N formulation in ethanol. (c) R2R printed PEI-Zn in 8:1 Zn-to-N formulation in ethanol.

reference cells (Glass/ITO/PEI-Zn/PM6:Y12/BM-HTL-1/Ag) and printed flexible devices were fabricated with different PEI-Zn Zn-to-N ratios with proof-printing equipment.

Both spin-coated and printed devices show similar photovoltaic performance for different Zn-to-N molar ratios (Figure 6(a) and (b)). This allows for more flexibility regarding ETL ink formulation for R2R gravure printing. The substantially lower current density of printed devices compared to spin-coated devices is investigated in detail elsewhere.

The deviation in printed devices (Figure 6(b)) is mainly attributed to less stable production conditions in ambient environment, compared to spin-coated devices fabricated in glovebox environment. At high Zn-to-N ratios, the ethanol-based PEI-Zn solution tends to form crystals within the printed layer (Figure S3(c)). This crystallization is attributed to oversaturation at high Zn concentrations, which is further promoted during printing by ethanol evaporation and by dried-in particles in the printing form that act as nucleation sites. As a result, recrystallization of zinc acetate or precipitation through hydrolysis can occur. Maintaining the formulation at elevated temperature during printing suppresses this crystallization to some extent.

The results shown in Figure 6 were obtained using a gravure proof printing setup. The proof printing setup uses the same cylinders and printing form as a large scale R2R printing unit but prints only one full circumference of the cylinder. A schematic drawing of the setup can be found in Figure S4. Printing only one full circumference drastically reduces material consumption, when a larger set of ink formulations needs to be tested. But it also simplifies the printing process and interaction between ink and gravure form, since every print-run has a perfectly clean printing form, which is not the case in a continuous process. In a continuous R2R gravure printing process, after contact of printing plate and substrate, a fraction of ink remains in the gravure form cells [39]. This fraction of remaining ink comes in contact with fresh ink on the next circumference and can influence the stability of the printing process. Therefore, proof printing setups are a good indicator for printability of an ink formulation and suitable printing and annealing parameters, but a continuous R2R process has to be tested and optimized separately.

For R2R gravure printing trials, two PEI-Zn formulations with Zn-to-N ratios of 15:1 and 8:1 were selected. While the 15:1 formulation yielded reproducible results in proof printing, it is prone to oversaturation during continuous R2R processing, where solvent evaporation and nucleation at particles in the printing form promote precipitation. Heating the printing cylinder and doctor blade unit to 45 °C was required to maintain formulation stability over hundreds of meters of print length (Figure 7(a)). Nevertheless, the 15:1 formulation produced strongly defective layers during continuous R2R printing, whereas the 8:1 formulation resulted in significantly fewer defects (Figure 7(b) and (c)). This behavior indicates that the ethanol-based PEI-Zn formulation with a 15:1 Zn-to-N ratio is close to its solubility limit, leading to recrystallization of zinc acetate or hydrolysis-derived precipitates during printing.

The R2R printed 8:1 PEI-Zn layers were used to create fully printed OSC devices with the subsequent layers

FIGURE 8 | J-V characteristics of fully printed OSCs with R2R printed PEI-Zn (black) and with PEI-Zn printed with a proof printing setup (red). For R2R printed PEI-Zn, the J-V characteristics of 3 devices are shown. PM6:Y12 in o-xylene active layer, BM-HTL-1, PEDOT:PSS and silver TE are fabricated with proof printing equipment.

produced with proof printing machinery as described in section 2.1. The active layer material PM6:Y12 was dissolved in o-xylene for this case in hindsight of fully R2R printable devices. Figure 8 shows a comparison of devices with PEI-Zn in 8:1 formulation gravure printed with R2R machinery (black) and proof printing equipment (red), both with o-xylene-based AL. The J-V characteristics of the resulting devices, depicted in Figure 8, are in good agreement with the results retrieved from proof-printing in Figure 6 and show very similar performance. This shows PEI-Zn can be employed as ETL in an industry scale gravure printing process for fully printed OSCs. While the proof printed devices are very consistent, there is more variance in the devices, where the ETL was fabricated in a continuous R2R fashion. This is attributed to the continuous process, where gravure cells are not fully empty after ink deposition, while in the proof printing environment, the printing form is perfectly clean for each printed sample. The best performing devices including the R2R printed ETL show $V_{OC} = 780$ mV, $J_{SC} = 13.33$ mA/cm², FF=65% and PCE=6.76%. The photovoltaic parameters are corrected with respect to J_{SC} measured under Wavelabs LS2 solar simulator. Since the LS2 spectrum deviates from AM1.5G (Figure S5(a)), J_{SC} was recalculated by integrating the measured EQE (Figure S5(b)) with the AM1.5G photon flux. The integrated EQE measured through a defined aperture also accounts for correcting an overestimation of J_{SC} due to the PEDOT:PSS layer extending beyond the silver electrode (Figure 1(a)). The extended geometry of the PEDOT:PSS layer would otherwise allow additional lateral charge collection.

3. | Conclusion

This study presents a gravure printable PEI-Zn ETL material in non-toxic solvent formulation as alternative to commonly used ZnO NP solution. We demonstrated the successful transfer of ETL materials from spin-coating to proof-printing and finally to industrial-scale R2R gravure printing in ambient conditions. For this lab-to-fab transfer, not only adjustments of rheological properties and solvent evaporation rate of ink formulations have to be considered, but also annealing conditions, chemical and mechanical compatibility of materials to subsequent layers and processes and possible influences of ambient conditions. The scalability of the PEI-Zn material and the gravure printing process is demonstrated by R2R printing PEI-Zn ETLs over hundreds of meters on flexible IMI-PET substrate. Furthermore, the viability of the PEI-Zn formulation as ETL is demonstrated in fully printed devices, showing similar performance to ZnO-based ETLs, while providing better adhesion to the substrate and mechanical robustness towards the subsequent printing processes.

Although the precipitation of PEI-Zn can be suppressed by heating the printing unit, doctor blade and ink chamber, further research should focus on making the formulation more stable for deposition under room temperature conditions.

3. | Experimental Section

Materials:

As functionalized substrates, PET-Foil coated with an indium tin oxide-Metal-indium tin oxide (IMI, $\sim 10 \Omega \text{ sq}^{-1}$) was used. The coated substrates were acquired from ASCA GmbH, Kitzingen, Germany. ZnO nanoparticle solution (N-12, 5 wt% in ethanol) was acquired from Avantama. Polyethyleneimine (PEI, Mw 25000) and zinc acetate dihydrate were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. PM6 donor and BTP-4F-C12 (Y12) acceptor materials and BM-HTL-1 were purchased from Brilliant Matters. PEDOT:PSS (ORGACON EL-P5015) was acquired from AGFA. Screen printing conductor paste (Loctite ECI 1011) was purchased from Henkel.

Device fabrication:

Fully printed OSC fabrication:

IMI-PET substrates were treated with an antistatic fan, cleaned with toluene, and UV treated prior to printing. ZnO:PVP was prepared by mixing ethanol-based ZnO nanoparticle solution N-12 with 50 vol. % 1-butanol and 1 wt. % PVP with molar mass 1300k was added. The PEI-Zn solutions were prepared by first dissolving 0.1 wt.% polyethyleneimine (PEI, Mw 25000) in ethanol. Depending on the Zn-to-N mole ratios, different amounts of zinc acetate dihydrate were added to the PEI-ethanol solution. For Zn-to-N mole ratios of 15:1/12:1/10:1/8:1, 75/60/50/40 mg/ml zinc acetate dihydrate were added to the PEI-ethanol solution. To improve the solubility of zinc acetate dihydrate in PEI-ethanol solution, 60 $\mu\text{l/ml}$ water was added. The PEI-Zn solution was stirred for 2 hours at 50 °C on a hotplate at 300 rpm and ultrasonicated at 50 °C for 10 minutes. The PEI-Zn solution is kept at 45 °C on a hotplate prior to gravure printing. For gravure printing an in-house developed R2R proof printing unit was used. ZnO:PVP and PEI-Zn were gravure printed respectively on non-structured, cleaned IMI-PET substrates at web speeds of 0.2 m/s using a gravure form with 14 ml/m² cavity volume. The gravure printed ETLs were annealed at 140 °C for 10 minutes in a box oven. For the active layer material, PM6 donor and Y12 acceptor were mixed in a 1:1.2 ratio, dissolved in a total weight concentration of 16 mg/ml and stirred over night at room temperature. Prior to printing, the PM6:Y12 solution is stirred on a hotplate at 45 °C for 1 hour. PM6:Y12 was gravure printed on the respective ETL using a gravure form with 22 ml/m² cavity volume at 0.2 m/s web speed. Printed ALs were annealed at 120°C for 5 min. IMI-PET substrates with gravure printed ETL and AL were cut into sheets for further processing steps. BM-HTL-1 was ultrasonicated for 30 minutes and filtered with a 0.45 μm PTFE filter. BM-HTL-1 was slot-die coated with a laboratory slot-die coater (L2005A2-50) from Ossila at a coating speed of 10 mm/s on a heated bed at 60°C and subsequently annealed at 120°C for 10 minutes on a hotplate. For deposition of ETL, AL and BM-HTL-1, a flow of nitrogen was employed to the substrate via air-knife for additional cleaning and drying. PEDOT:PSS (Orgacon EL-P5015) buffer layer is screen printed on top of BM-HTL-1 using a semi-automatic screen printing unit (EKRA X1) with a 120-34 PE mesh. PEDOT:PSS is dried in a box oven at 130°C for 10 minutes. The Ag top electrodes are screen printed using LOCTITE ECI 1011 E&C silver ink and a 100-40 PE mesh. Silver top electrodes are annealed at 130°C for 10 minutes.

Spin-coated reference device fabrication:

Inverted reference devices were fabricated in the device architecture glass/ITO/PEI-Zn/PM6:Y12/BM-HTL-1/Ag. ITO-coated glass substrates were cleaned with deionized water and isopropanol. PEI-Zn in ethanol solution with Zn-to-N mole ratios of 15:1/12:1/10:1/8:1 was spin-coated on ITO substrate at 4000 rpm for 45 s and thermally annealed at 140 °C for 10 min. PM6:Y12 (1:1.2) was dissolved in chloroform in a total weight concentration of 12 mg/ml, spin-coated onto the substrates and annealed at 100 °C for 10 min. BM-HTL-1 was spin-coated at 3000 rpm for 50 s on pre-heated substrates and thermally annealed at 100 °C for 5 min. Finally, 100 nm Ag was thermally evaporated with a shadow mask as top electrodes.

Characterization:

J-V measurements were carried out under inert nitrogen atmosphere inside a glovebox. The JV characteristics were acquired using a Keithley 2450 source-measure unit. Characterization of the solar cells under simulated solar illumination was done with a Wavelabs LS2 solar simulator. Microscopy was done with a Keyence Laser Scanning Microscope. Layer thickness measurements were done with a Dektak Stylus Profilometer (Dektak XT-A). The EQE of devices was measured using wavelength-resolved monochromatic illumination provided by a Bentham monochromator.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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FIGURE S1 | J-V-characteristics of spin-coated devices processed in ambient air and glovebox environment with PM6:Y12 active layer material.

FIGURE S2 | Laser scanning microscope images of gravure cell wall impressions in ZnO layers with increasing UVO-treatment from left (none) to right (3x). After UVO-treatment ZnO layers were printed on with gravure printing using o-xylene to simulate AL printing. Images (a)-(c) taken at 20x magnification, (d)-(f) at 50x.

FIGURE S3 | (a) Layer quality of PEI-Zn layer in 2-methoxyethanol solvent. (b) Layer quality of PEI-Zn layer in ethanol-based solvent. (c) Crystal formation in printed PEI-Zn layer. Inset shows sample at 150x magnification, the scale bar in the inset shows 10 μm .

FIGURE S4 | Schematic drawing of gravure proof printing unit (left). R2R gravure printing unit at Laborman II printing machine (right).

FIGURE S5 | (a) Emission spectrum of the Wavelabs LS2 solar simulator in comparison with the AM1.5G reference spectrum. (b) Short-circuit current density obtained by integrating the EQE with the LS2 and AM1.5G spectra.